

EOSC Risk Governance

**Support the strengthening of the
EOSC Risk Governance through
the implementation of an effective
Risk Management System**

**Executive Summary
30 September 2020**

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Executive Summary

The European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is the European Commission initiative aimed at developing an infrastructure to connect Research Data with (e-Infrastructure) Tools & Services, eventually providing its users with services for *open science* practices.

A key objective of the Sustainability Working Group is to provide recommendations and advise for the implementation of an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation after 2020. The sustainability of EOSC depends not only on sound financial, legal and business models and their different implications, but also on governance models aiming to add value for the stakeholders and to encourage research bodies' as well as researcher's participation predominantly as well.

Under the EOSCsecretariat.eu co-creation funding, Aon Risk Consulting Italy produced a preliminary analysis of the current and future EOSC risk governance.

The main outcomes, considerations and recommendations of the study are reported in this document.

The Study

This study aims at identifying, analysing and evaluating the main gaps present in the EOSC risk governance structure with respect to Risk Governance best practices, as well as mapping the risk macro areas to support the future implementation of EOSC.

The study also proposes some guidelines on how to move forward in structuring and nurturing the risk management governance of EOSC.

The study has been developed by the Italian team of Aon Hewitt Risk & Consulting, based in Milan, over a period of 20 weeks (May-October 2020).

This document represents the final report of the study and is proposed ahead of schedule to allow for alignment and to ensure the maximum support to the interim EOSC governing bodies in the various development activities that are being rolled out in these months (i.e. the SRIA document, the EOSC Association with its founding members, etc.).

The document is structured in the following sections:

- an **Assessment of the internal and the external context of EOSC** (i.e. EOSC organisational structure, EOSC's stakeholders and kind-of similar organisations/associations that have commonalities with EOSC);
- a **Gap Analysis** of the future governance with respect to the best practice;
- a **High-Level Risk Assessment** and the list of the risks identified, classified and quantitatively evaluated;
- **Guideline solutions** to cover the gaps on the risk governance and to manage the identified risks;
- a **map of the governance recommendations and the risks** to the action areas of SRIA;
- concluding considerations and potential next steps.

AON has studied, analysed and assessed the governance structure of EOSC – both the interim governance in place up until December 2020 and the future EOSC governance (post 2020) – to understand the complex context in which EOSC operates, the variety of stakeholders involved and the maturity of the EOSC governance systems vs the assessment and management of risks.

AON, at this stage of the development of the study feels compelled to state that it has embraced this challenge with great enthusiasm. It is also understandable that AON is in a sense unaware of the complete and intricate policy and technical complexities surrounding EOSC, considering it has not been involved in any EOSC related activity up until this commissioned study. Nevertheless, in these short months, it has understood the complexities involved from the different major European stakeholders depending on their maturity level of EOSC activity as well as the vision from the European Commission. All of these stakeholders wanting to embark on such an important and relevant initiative for the European Science and Research and Innovation community.

Moreover, despite the high-level and articulated number of identified risks in the present report, AON is confident that this endeavour has the right competences and skill set on board from the different stakeholders to support such a relevant and necessary European objective. The goal being to support and protect European technical sovereignty in terms of both research and e-infrastructures, as well Europe's renowned data research management services and valuable data sets potentially available to millions of researchers and AON looks forward to seeing some of these results become an integral part of the implementation phase.

The assessment was performed on the basis of:

- analysing over 20 official documents, reports and presentations produced by EOSC;
- analysing the outcomes from the EOSCsecretariat.eu (EOSC Liaison Platform) and participation in the EOSC Consultation Day - at the Sustainability Working Group session - where the risk management study was mentioned;
- providing a benchmark analysis of over 6 organisations and associations that have been chosen that are comparable to a complex EOSC structure (for domain, complexity of its organisational structure and political influence, from multiple parties in the decision making). For the details, the reader may refer to section 4 of the present document;
- assessing the outcomes from a set of interviews on a panel of 14 key resources of EOSC, conducted from June 15th to July 17th 2020. The interviews were arranged to gather an overview of the EOSC initiative, governance and risks directly from its stakeholders. The interviewees were selected to represent a sufficiently various mix across several dimensions: competences (e.g. governing roles, funding members, research infrastructure and e-infrastructure communities), cultural awareness (e.g. technical staff, policy makers, managers, researchers), nationalities (9 countries) and stakeholder groups (e.g. research communities, Member States, European Commission). For the details, the reader may refer to section 5 of the present document;
- drawing on the long-standing expertise and experience of the AON's risk consultancy specialists in designing and implementing risk governance models in a large variety of firms, public entities and other customers, worldwide.

It should be noted that some confidential documents might not have been brought to AON's attention, for legitimate reasons, therefore some of the conclusions may be subject to revision should this further evidence be disclosed in due time.

Gap analysis: main outcomes

The main outcomes that emerged from the gap analysis activities that are elaborated in the following sections may be summed up as follows:

- EOSC operates within a **multiple factor environment** and with a high degree of complexity affecting the governance structure. The factors include organisational model, political influences, transnationality and cross-disciplinary usership;
- a **clear and defined risk governance structure** with assigned roles and responsibilities for risk management has not yet been established;
- **specific policies and procedures** supporting the risk governance are lacking;
- some skills, experience and attention to risk governance are present within the organisation, nevertheless they appear scattered and fragmented, and perhaps far from a synergistic and organic integration within an articulated and rigorous governance framework;
- risk management activities for EOSC have been limited to project-based analysis and therefore fragmented across the numerous EOSC projects, which are still ongoing for a number of years in the future. An overall risk assessment of EOSC has not yet been performed and a reporting process to allow structured decisions on risks has not yet been defined;
- the missions of the Association and of EOSC Ecosystem are only partially overlapping.

EOSC needs to significantly strengthen its Risk Management System, in order to:

- increase the value of the EOSC Association and benefit to its stakeholders;
- support its business objectives and allow for a more effective use and allocation of capital and resources within the organisation;
- achieve the above by protecting the assets, the corporate brand, the know-how of the key people, and also by optimizing the operational efficiency.

48 gaps were identified from the analysis of the EOSC's risk governance, across various dimensions and components (i.e. risk governance and culture, strategy setting, performance evaluation, review and revision and communication to name a few).

A 5-grade scale was introduced to map the gaps between the EOSC's future governance and the reference best practices (1: maximum adherence to the best practice, 5: maximum distance from the reference).

The following chart shows how the EOSC's risk governance structure has been assessed vs the best practice.

Gap score distribution of EOSC risk governance

This study sets out **32 recommendations** to cover all of the 48 gaps (details about the gaps are reported in section 5) to ensure the effectiveness of an EOSC risk governance.

The main recommendations being as follows:

1. **Launch a comprehensive plan** to address these gaps and define a risk governance framework and organisation primarily instrumental to supporting the structuring and development process of EOSC itself; such an entity should enrol resources with adequate skills, expertise and experience in designing and implementing ERM frameworks.
2. **Establish a governance structure for risk management** that is clear, effective, adequate and well formalised, and appoint roles and responsibilities across the organisational structure (i.e. Risk Management Control Committee, Chief Risk Officer and his/her team with corresponding budget, Risk Owners, etc.);
3. **Define the EOSC ERM Policies** for regulating roles and responsibilities within the risk governance structure. The policies serve as the strategic guidance reference for risk management and regulate the interactions between the different stakeholders;
4. **Design the Risk Assessment & Reporting Process** that properly analyse all the main risk areas, including strategic areas and alignment with EOSC's mission and vision, that are affected by internal and external environment (e.g. politics, economy, technological development, regulations, society), and enhances risk intelligence;
5. **Map the skills and competences** required to perform an effective risk management at different levels of the association in order to consider all the fields of competence involved in the initiative (e.g. strategy, economics and finance, ICT technologies, Cyber Security, international relations, regulatory, programme and project management, project risk management) and **set requirements** on the composition of risk management bodies **to assure independence in decision-making**.

For each gap, a set of recommendations have been suggested to improve the risk governance components (an example is reported in the figure below). For the details on the governance recommendations proposed for each gap, the reader may refer to section 7 of the document.

Example of recommendation structure

PRINCIPLES	OBJECTIVES	FUTURE GOVERNANCE OF EOSC ASSOCIATION	GAP SCORE	RECOMMENDATION	NEW GAP SCORE
1. Governance and Culture					
1.1 Exercises Board Risk Oversight	1.1.1 Accountability and Responsibility	EOSC Statute defines the board's and respective responsibilities, but among these the responsibility for risk oversight and risk management has not been assigned.	4	GR1 GR2	2

The figure below shows the distribution of the gaps on the risk governance before and after the implementation of the proposed recommendations.

Gap score distribution of EOSC risk governance before and after recommendations

The proposed governance recommendations provide benefits on EOSC governance by reducing the gaps with respect of the best practice. However, to fully cover these gaps, the risk governance is usually reassessed, tested and adapted to the challenges (both internal and external) arising from the introduction of an ERM framework. For this reason, it is of the utmost importance for EOSC to implement an ERM Framework with care, attention and involving specific professionals in the sector able to manage and keep the implementation phase under control.

Risk assessment outcomes

During the risk governance assessment, AON identified also **30 risks** that may affect the second phase of the EOSC implementation (after 2020) and subdivided them into five categories specifically defined for EOSC (i.e. financial, governance, operational reputational and strategic). These risks have been prioritised by quantitatively evaluating the likelihood of occurrence and the potential impact and graphically reported in the heat-map. For the all the details about the risks, the reader may refer to section 6 of the document.

A number of key drivers that act on multiple risks and may jeopardise participation in the EOSC Association and adoption of its services have been identified. In particular:

- the absence of a clear and formalised risk governance and risk management structure;
- the incomplete and not yet formalised definition of the value proposition for each stakeholder (internal and external to the Association);
- the incomplete definition of the economic-financial plan and a budget to ensure the long-term financial sustainability of EOSC;
- the absence of the definitions of roles, responsibilities in case, process and procedure to intervene in case of system failure.

Similarly, to the governance, the study proposes a set of **35 risk management recommendations** that should be put in place in order to deal with the identified risks. For the details about the risk recommendations proposed, the reader may refer to section 7 of the document.

The main risk management recommendations are:

1. **Design and implement the “EOSC ERM framework”** that need to be continuously monitored, improved and updated, especially in case of substantial changes (on strategy, organisational structure, boundary conditions, etc) and in case of occurrence of risks that have material impacts;
2. **Set up and lead a process to continuously analyse and closely monitor the risks that may jeopardise the execution of the identified strategy** and the achievement of the strategic objectives and the most relevant measurable targets, also leveraging through the continuous monitoring of a specific and wide set of strategic KPIs and KRIs that should be designed and implemented;
3. **Set-up an infrastructure and data security team (or committee)** accountable for:
 - design, update and share cyber security, business continuity and disaster recovery policy;
 - design a process that ensure the quality of the data, especially research data, and data services;
 - define a catalogue of potential risks (e.g. cyber-attacks, business interruption, damage to data, failure of systems or applications, etc);
 - define a risk assessment methodology in order to estimate potential impacts of the risk’s occurrence;
 - support the definition, based on risk assessment and risk management best practices, of several levels of responsibilities in case of failures;
 - evaluate specific insurance programmes that consider both direct and indirect causes of the risks;
4. **Draft and implement a Project Risk Management policy**, which ensure that each project involving EOSC has an appointed project risk manager and an effective risk assessment and treatment plan in place;
5. **Establish a risk awareness programme** to support and enhance the culture and skills in risk management across EOSC;
6. **Improve technical resilience** of EOSC infrastructures by:
 - performing specific business impact analysis (i.e. risk assessment, quantitative estimation of risk impact) and identifying the most relevant business interruption risk causes;
 - defining, introducing and updating the business continuity management plan;
 - drafting and testing the disaster recovery plan;
 - defining a set of binding rules about resilience, business continuity management plan and disaster recovery plan on which service providers have to be compliant with.

The figure below shows the distribution of the risks on the Heat Map before (AS IS) and after (TO BE) the implementation of the proposed recommendations.

It should be noted, looking at the evolution of the risk map, that the proposed measures significantly reduce the risk profile, but not conclusively. This is clearer if we understand that most of the risks addressed are of a strategic or governance nature. Only the complete and holistic structuring of EOSC governance and adequate EOSC risk governance will allow to capture the synergies between the different actions and to reduce the risk profile represented.

Main Conclusions

The research system in Europe is in transition. It is facing growing challenges related to global competition, technological change, increasing complexity, the need to leverage more and more data as raw material. As a result, it feels it must become increasingly open, collaborative, crossing all kinds of boundaries.

Moreover, the effects of the global pandemic are having a significant impact on the technology sector, disrupting the electronics value chain, affecting raw materials supply and causing an inflationary risk on products. From a positive perspective, the disruption has caused an acceleration of remote working, and a rapid focus on evaluating and de-risking the end-to-end value chain¹.

An environment of this type, obviously, has multiple factors of complexity and leads to a significant number of risks that may drive the EOSC implementation process to a partial or overall failure with respect of the objectives and the planned activities.

In order to perform the analysis, AON has identified the best and most up-to-date practices suitable for articulated and complex international organisational structures and has followed an open approach aimed at deepening the peculiarities in terms of internal and external environment and analysing the real EOSC's needs.

The assessment has allowed Aon to obtain an in-depth knowledge of EOSC governance and environmental context including risk culture, core values, behaviours, and decision-making activities and the constraints which EOSC deals with. It has emerged that EOSC

¹ <https://www2.deloitte.com/global/en/pages/about-deloitte/articles/covid-19/understanding-covid-19-s-impact-on-the-technology-sector-.html>

mission is not limited to only linking datasets, federating infrastructures and aligning policies, but it starts by harmonizing multiple stakeholders across the European research and political ecosystem, and aligning their mission and their vision.

At the same time as this study has been developed, the EOSC Association has been established and the SRIA document is in development, requiring a major effort to the organisational structuring and identification of the strategic guidelines that will lead EOSC forward in the coming years.

It is worth to note that, AON has found a human capital very rich in multidisciplinary technical skills, sensitivity to governance issues, passion for the activities to be carried out and for the belief in EOSC itself. Moreover, the presence of all, or almost all, the essential pillars for the construction of effective risk management has been found. The EOSC major players who AON conversed with during the study showed an interest and awareness of the importance of the subject that was very high and mutual amongst the relevant players as well as the relevant skills and experience in the different areas of risk management are spread among stakeholders even if currently they are not systematically introduced in a complete and effective risk governance.

The main findings that emerged from the gap analysis, as partially expected, were related to the weakness of the governance process in which competences are not organically integrated and structured for the management of the overall spectrum of risks. During the analysis a definition of risk governance roles and responsibilities was not detected, nor a clear definition of policies and procedures supporting the risk governance.

Starting from the analyses carried out, AON proposed a set of mitigation strategies as the starting point for the design phase of the governance system that will allow EOSC to manage its risks and make the initiative sustainable in the long term.

The blue print of the next phase that AON recommends is articulated as follows:

- set-up a small working group that has the necessary commitment and represents a correct mix of skills and representation of stakeholders' interests;
- identify a figure endowed with the necessary experience and analysis skills to guide the project of ERM deployment, able to provide a holistic vision of the areas affected by risks, and manage the complexity by proposing different alternatives and transforming them, once identified, into operational processes and matrices of responsibility;
- integrate the main recommendations of risk management and analysis of the interdependencies between areas in the SRIA evolution;
- set-up and lead a process to continuously analyse and closely monitor the risks that may jeopardise the execution of the identified strategy and the achievement of the strategic objectives and the most relevant measurable targets, also leveraging through the continuous monitoring of a specific and wide set of strategic KPIs and KRIs that should be designed and implemented;
- set the priorities on the governance objectives to be targeted and design an incremental plan to achieve them.